

Oral session: Psychosocial interventions 2

16:30 - 17:45 Thursday, 7th July, 2022

Room 36

Presentation type Oral session

Chair Irene Niks

O118 How Does Your Work Serve a Greater Good? Short, Online Meaning Interventions Can Boost Momentary Work Engagement Through Changes in Work Meaningfulness (Remote presentation)

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Abstract

We employed a novel approach to examine how meaning-making processes can enhance psychological functioning at the work place. Namely, we developed short, online meaning intervention and tested its effect on momentary work engagement and perceived work meaningfulness. In Study 1 (N = 227) we asked employees to write why their work was meaningful. This led to higher work meaningfulness experience and higher momentary work engagement (MWE) compared to a control group. The relationship between the intervention and MWE was mediated with work meaningfulness. In Study 2 (N = 254), employees were asked to either write about how one's work serves a greater good (other-oriented meaning intervention) vs. how it advances personal career (self-oriented meaning intervention), vs. control. Relative to the control, other-oriented meaning intervention increased work meaningfulness. The latter mediated the relationship between the other-oriented meaning intervention and MWE. The studies develop new research methods that can be easily and widely applied and offer fresh insight into how sources of meaningful work are related to important occupational outcomes.

O119 Daily Work Stress and Unhealthy Snacking: The Moderating Role of Trait Mindfulness

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Abstract

Unhealthy snacking is considered one of the main contributors to the current obesity pandemic with nearly a third of the world's population being obese nowadays (World Health Organization, 2020). Shedding light onto the factors that may contribute to snacking and weight gain is therefore crucial both from a theoretical and practical perspective. Clinical studies have persistently reported stress as one of the most important factors for changes in eating behavior (Hill et al., 2018; Scott & Johnstone, 2012) and first empirical evidence suggests that work stress, in comparison to other types of stress, has particularly strong effects on food choice (O'Connor et al., 2008). Nevertheless, although some studies on the impact of work stress on snacking emerged in the past years, they mainly focused on rather coarse and distal indicators of work stress (e.g., work hours; Jones et al., 2007; Wardle et al., 2000) and rather chronic, between-person differences (Clohessy et al., 2019), providing little insights into *when* and *why* work demands affect snacking.

Yet, since snacking takes place on an *intrapersonal* level and naturally fluctuates from day to day, the overall goal of our study is to adopt a within-person perspective in studying the fundamental mechanisms linking work demands to snacking behavior. Drawing on COR theory (Hobfoll, 1989), we suggest two pathways that may explain how work stress relates to unhealthy snacking: self-regulation and affect regulation. When faced with stressful situations at work, individuals may attempt to distract themselves and regulate their negative experiences by turning to unhealthy snacks because they believe that it will alleviate the stressful experience and make them feel better (Berset et al., 2011; Ulrich-Lai et al., 2015). In turn, an important personality trait that may act as a buffer between negative work experiences and unhealthy snacking is mindfulness, as individuals with high trait mindfulness are able to experience negative encounters without impulsively reacting to them (Alberts et al., 2012).

To test our hypotheses, we collected diary data across two workweeks (10 working days). The final sample included 120 employees who responded to three daily surveys measuring their experiences at work and in the evening after work. Results did not show a significant linear relationship between daily work stress and unhealthy snacking. The protective nature of trait mindfulness became apparent, with individuals high in trait mindfulness snacking less when emotionally exhausted in the evening after work. From a practical point of view, this is promising, as mindfulness can be improved with training for employees with lower natural levels (van de Veer et al., 2012). Additionally, supplementary analysis revealed

behaviors. To protect employees, organizations may evaluate current job roles and consider potential job enlargement and job enrichment strategies.

0120 Skin Cancer Prevention Through the Promotion of Sun Protection Behaviors at Work: A Systematic Review of Randomized Control Trials

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Abstract

During the last years, there is an alarming increase in the incidence rates of skin cancer (Sung et al., 2020). The main extrinsic risk factor for skin cancer is exposure to solar ultraviolet radiation (UVR); therefore, raising awareness and challenging certain ideas about sunbaths and tanning together with regular sunscreen use seems to be key measures to prevent this kind of cancer in people who work outdoors and are regularly exposed to the sun (Green et al., 2011).

We conducted a systematic review aimed at answering the following questions: (a) what are the most effective techniques to raise awareness about the risk of excessive exposure to UVR and promote sun protection behaviors at work? And (b) what explanatory models of behavior serve as the basis for skin cancer prevention programs in the workplace?

Articles were selected if they met the following criteria: (1) The study population was composed of working adults; (2) The study aimed at preventing skin cancer in the workplace through the promotion of protective behaviors from exposure to UVR; (3) The study used a Randomized Control Trial (RCT) design and reported quantitative analyses of the effectiveness of the intervention; and (4) The study was published, in English, Portuguese or Spanish, in a peer-reviewed journal from January 1, 2016 to June 30, 2021.

After inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, the final sample comprised 9 articles. Our results revealed that seven articles are aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of the Sun Safe Workplace (SSW) program. Six of these articles are guided by the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Buller et al., 2020; Buller et al., 2018; Buller et al., 2019; Buller et al., 2021; Walkosz et al., 2018; Walkosz et al., 2019), which is a sociological approach that considers different factors when persuading people to adopt innovations like the introduction of new preventive measures to reduce a health risk at work (see Rogers, 2002). Therefore, the SSW program implements four measures: (1) persuading senior managers to adopt solar safety policies (e.g., developing protocols that consider the risk of developing skin cancer due to exposure to solar radiation); (2) raising workers' awareness about the risk of skin cancer and how to reduce it; (3) providing sun protection equipment (caps or shirts and long-sleeved vests) and sunscreens; and (4) facilitating personalized messages that remind workers the effective ways to protect themselves from the UVR. In addition, there is another study that implements the SSW program but following the principles of the Health Belief Model (Duffy et al., 2018).

The other two studies used text messages via mobile phone (hence its name SunSmart) to persuade workers of their ability to carry out preventive behavior and the importance of the consequences of this type of action. These studies were based on the Protection Motivation Theory (Heydari et al., 2021) and the Theory of Reasoned Action (Lansdown et al., 2020), respectively.

Overall, when the intervention group is compared with the control group, findings revealed that skin prevention programs are effective.

0121 Just-in-Time Adaptive Interventions for Dealing With Work Stress and With the Challenges of Shift Work

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Abstract

A just-in-time adaptive intervention (JITAI) "is an intervention design aiming to provide the right type/amount of support, at the right time, by adapting to an individual's changing internal and contextual state" (Nahum-Shani et al., 2018, p. 1). In other words, the goal of JITAI is to address the changing needs of individuals for support. JITAIs are increasingly used to promote health behavior change (Carpenter et al., 2020; Nahum-Shani et al., 2018).

We developed two JITAI-prototypes. One prototype's goal is supporting health care professionals in managing their daily work stress. The other prototype aimed at supporting shift workers with the challenges of working irregular hours and at night. Both prototypes operate in a smartphone application (How-Am-I-app). At the end (and/or start) of each shift, the app prompts the user to fill in a short questionnaire on stress, workload, recovery, fatigue and context-related factors. Immediately after this assessment, the developed algorithm results in personalized feedback and provides the user with suitable tips.

autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in managing their daily stress levels. SAM provides users with direct feedback on their stress levels, personal tips to reduce their stress, and insight in their individual stress patterns by providing statistics.

In the presentation we will illustrate the potential of the JITAI-prototype by showing results of SAM. Also, we will reflect on lessons learned and future challenges for other JITAIs aimed at reducing work stress and supporting shift workers.

O122 Learning in the Workplace for Health and Well-Being: Building Bridges and Insights From a Secondary Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

In a constantly changing organizational environment, learning in the workplace is more important than ever for workers' health and well-being. There is now a vast literature that contributes greatly to our understanding of how workers learn and develop. Yet, there are multiple approaches when it comes to learning – from formal approaches such as training and coaching to newer approaches like informal learning. This silo approach leaves potential for untapped synergies.

We therefore aim to bridge those research silos and take stock of what is known so far with the help of a combined narrative review and secondary meta-analysis. More specifically, we identify which approaches to learning in the workplace have been investigated until to date, how they are defined, and which outcomes they can achieve. This contributes to answering the question of which learning approaches are potentially more effective than others for workers' health and well-being. Importantly, we have a look at the factors that may explain their differential effectiveness, such as individualization, involvement, and technology.

To identify literature to include in our secondary meta-analysis, we searched Web of Science Core Collection. We identified and checked 621 potential articles for inclusion. We incorporated primary meta-analyses that investigated at least one learning approach, in relation to the workplace, and were written in English. For instance, we excluded primary meta-analyses that solely relied on student samples (oftentimes medical students) or when learning was not the goal of the workplace intervention. In total, we included 66 primary meta-analyses. All studies were published in peer-reviewed journals, between 1994 and 2021.

The results show that research on learning in the workplace investigates a plethora of learning approaches. Most studies analyzed training, followed by other approaches such as coaching and mentoring. Many studies did not prespecify the learning approach and investigated workplace interventions with learning components, such as burnout prevention interventions. The included meta-analyses varied greatly regarding the specificity of the learning approaches. Where some primary meta-analyses included a wide array of different studies within one learning approach (such as training for diverse purposes), other meta-analyses focused on specific target groups (predominantly the health professions), specific goals (for instance, reducing injury rates), or specific approaches (for instance, mindfulness-based stress reduction). We identified common questions across the learning approaches, especially the influence of technology (f2f, blended, or virtual), individualization, simulation, involvement, and setting (on or off-the-job). Regarding the effectiveness of the different learning approaches and the factors that may explain them, the final results of the quantitative analyses will be presented in July.

Summing up, we deliver an integrated perspective on 30 years of research on learning in the workplace and workers' health and well-being. Our findings eventually help organizations, HRD professionals, and workers navigating through these different learning approaches to help them make informed decisions about what can help them best for their health and well-being.